

THE IMPORTANCE OF AN EDUCATIONAL APPROACH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE EMOTIONAL SPHERE OF STUDENTS OF A SMALL SCHOOL AGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019649>

Tuychieva Shoyista Jumaboyevna

NamDU 3rd course doktorant UBS teacher

Annotaytsiya: *Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolani shaxs sifatida shakillanishi. Pivojlanishning ma'lum bosqichi sifatidagi ahamiyati. Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar emotsional sohasida oilaning o'ziga hosliklari. Ta'lim jarayonida emotsional barqarorlikning(oilaning) ahamiyati.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Emotsiya, emotsional barqarorlik, ta'lim samaradorligi,*

Annatatsion: *The formation of a child's a person of junior school age. Importance as a certain stage of development. Peculiarities of the emotional sphere of children of primery school age. The importance of emotional stability in the educational process.*

Key word: *emotion, emotional stability, educational efficiency.*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *Личность маленького ребенка школьного возраста шаткая как личность. Важность на определенной стадии развития. Особенности эмоциональной сферы детей младшего школьного возраста. Значение эмоциональной устойчивости в образовательном процессе.*

Ключевые слова: *эмоциональность, эмоциональная устойчивость, образовательная эффективность.*

In today's globalization process, there is a growing interest in the human factor and its study. Accordingly, we are witnessing advances in all branches of psychology. In this sense, the psychology of development is also fulfilling the obligations to it, many scientific problems are being solved at the time of the individual-general approach to age periods. The small school age period in particular has its significance in this regard. Many scientists have done research in this direction. An example of this is B.G. Was a theory proposed by Anan'ev, who developed a new methodological style in the study of the human psyche. He distinguished four basic qualities inherent in man: individuality, subject activity, personality, and individuality. This style is followed by a cornerstone in the holy shrine of the family. Itimoi and family relations ... one of the foundations of the child's experience is the social character in it, which is formed under the influence of the parent, family. I.e.

Methods of raising a child in a family according to parenting behavior

Style of upbringing	Protexia	Needs satisfaction	Suitabilit	Prohibition	Sanction
Excessive care Show	+	+	-	-	-

erprotection					
From care the inant hyperprotexius	+	+ -	+ -	+	+
Excess moral onsibility	+	-	+	+ -	+ -
Emotional raddia	-	-	+ -	+ -	+ -
Over austerities	-	-	+ -	+ +	+ -
Hypoprotection	-	-	-	-	+ -

On the basis of these criteria, it is possible to distinguish between the methods of raising parents' own children in different families. Hyperprotection is the excessive attention of parents to their children, which is manifested in their lack of strength, time and attention for the upbringing of the child. The parent makes this work a way of life, that is, both for the mother and for the father, the child's upbringing becomes an idyll of the meaning of his life. Hyperprotection is the attempt by parents to satisfy all the wishes, wishes and needs of the child blindly, without criticism and consideration; actions aimed at protecting the child from all difficulties and obstacles, fulfilling all his wishes on the spot, pampering him, rejoicing at his simple achievements, not noticing his mistakes. Those who "sacrifice their lives" for their children usually don't realize that they are doing harm to their children without knowing it, as a result, the child becomes impatient in the future, unable to control himself in the crowd, feeling helpless in the ups and downs of life, critical, will remain a man. Especially when the child reaches the age of adolescence, we want to show his aspiration for leadership, because he is a man, critical, wants to be what everyone says even in the circle of friends and peers, and secondly, he actually has such qualities. The point is that in such cases, the parents want to realize their dreams in the form of their offspring, which were not achieved in their life experience before, their upbringing methods are aimed at this, but the child feels that he is helpless in many ways when he gets into different situations of the social environment. starts Hyperprotection, which is superior to care, means paying attention to the child by controlling his every step and behavior rather than pampering. Therefore, various prohibitions and limitations ("it is not possible", "this is not possible") are common in this education method. A child who grows up in such conditions usually cannot be an independent thinker and independent decision-maker, but grows up to be angry and dissatisfied with many things, because he needs constant control, all the instructions of others. He gets used to being shown and told: he cannot prepare lessons without his mother, he cannot go out without his father, all he gets used to the intervention of adults in his work. Very strong moral responsibility -

in this case, the level of demands on the child from the parents is high, but his original desires and needs are not taken into account. Parents think about the future of their child and feel responsible for their behavior, they try to create a person in their personal imagination, to form a personality, sometimes under the control of the child's age, mental or physical capabilities, assignments are also given. For example, in the meaning of "you are our first-born, you should take care of your siblings", he is assigned responsible and difficult tasks such as taking care of the younger members of the family or a sick family member. Emotional rejection - in this, parents raise their child in such a way that they are regularly reminded that he is a worry, an excess burden in their parents' life, and that without him, the life of the parents would be different. If this child is not the only one in the family, but there is another, cheaper, more beloved person, the situation becomes more difficult, "if it wasn't for you..." or looking at the girl: "if only there was a boy in your place" such incidents are often mentioned. Some parents try to hide their emotional rejection of their child, "why don't you like the child?" even though he insists that he really should love him to such questions, the child still feels that it is too much trouble for his parents and wants to become independent as soon as possible, leave them, live separately. No matter how much the mother tries to artificially show her kindness, the child still feels in her heart that they are not sincere. Especially in cases where the father has separated or the father has abandoned him, such a mother's attitude is very hard on the child. At first glance, stubbornness is similar to emotional rejection, but it is more open and severe. Strictness can be in the form of beating a child directly from a young age, insulting, humiliating, or complete indifference to the child's needs, as if not noticing his or her presence. In both cases, the child tries to grow up as soon as possible, to make a living on his own, to get rid of the pressure of his parents. In such a family, it becomes a habit to punish the child for one or another behavior.

adults do not know that the child obeys the parents' judgment because of fear, and that this has bad consequences in the future, even if they know, this method seems effective for them. Methods such as guilt and appropriate punishment become a psychological factor controlling the child's behavior, and he learns to always look for culprits in the future. According to A. Freud's theory, a child sentenced to such a punishment becomes more and more aggressive, grows up as a vindictive person who is determined to take pain from some object (smaller than himself, strangers, animals). . According to data, at least 1% of street children in America are victims of such education in the family. The American scientist S.D. Sherrits (2003) studied the negative effects of such harshness in the family on the behavior of children and parents, and focused on the changes that occur in their character. Physically, they are small and unique, typical of representatives of almost all social strata. Most of the women who were unlucky in life and work or were victims of unhappy love, but gave birth to children, have a tendency to take their pain from their children, which is increasingly becoming a life skill. Especially under the influence of stress factors, parents (for example, unemployed, homeless, migrants who

went to other places in search of work, victims of ethnic or financial conflicts, poor) were born unable to solve their social problems. begins to take revenge on his child. Hypoprotection is a situation in which the parents either do not have enough time to deal with the child, or they leave this work to others. Some parents live like this and do not control their children at all. In the hidden form of hypopreception, it is as if the parents do something in the name of the child. But in fact, they are only interested in their daily problems. The child analyzes these situations and realizes that he is not needed, that he is superfluous in the family. Today, in many families, the parents themselves do not know the correct approach to child education, or, if they do, the obligations of the standard of living force them to ignore such situations. Otherwise, many parents believe that the approach to their children is the most correct approach. These and similar situations create the atmosphere in the family. Sometimes these manifestations provide a positive environment, and in other cases it is the opposite. This creates psychopathological conditions that increase the neurotic system among children. In turn, the reason is the lack of psychological knowledge and experience, responsibility and a serious approach to child education. Psychological prophylactic knowledge and experience are required from ordinary mothers, and taking into account these needs, we present the "Zunga" method, which is designed to measure the level of the neurotic system, as an application. After all, it is not surprising that this method plays the role of a preventive tool that should be in every family.

V.Zunga Test Answer Sheet.

Last name patronymic name. _____

numeric. _____

Instructions: The 10 questions below are reverse graded (2, 5, 6, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20) No, it is not like that 4 points, it must be like that 3 points, correct 2 points, very correct 1 point.

No	Situations No	not so	Probably so	True	Very
1.	I am depressed, in a state of sadness.				
2.	In the morning I feel better than ever.				
3.	I have periods of crying or tears.				
4.	I have a bad night's sleep.				
5.	My appetite is not worse than usual.				
6.	I enjoy looking at, talking to, and going out with other attractive looking men.				
7.	I feel like I'm losing weight.				
8.	Constipation bothers me.				
9.	My heart is beating faster than usual.				

10.	I'm getting tired for no reason.				
11.	I'm thinking as clear as ever.				
12.	It is easy for me to do what I know.				
13.	I feel restless and cannot sit still.				
14.	I have hope for my future.				
15.	I'm more nervous than usual.				
16.	My decision is easy.				
17.	I feel needed and needed.				
18.	I live a full enough life.				
19.	I feel that it would be better for others ie.				
20.	Things that always make me happy make me happy.				

Analysis of results. Note: The following 10 questions are reverse graded (2, 5, 6, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20) No not true 4 points, yes 3 points, correct 2 points, very correct 1 point.

1) Correctly evaluated (1, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 13, 15, 19) from the sum of cavols

2) Reverse evaluated (2, 5, 6, 11, 12, 14, 16, 17, 18, 20) subtract the sum of questions and add 35 to the result.

$(1 - 2) + 35 = RX$ 0 - 40 points in depressive state with low normal there is a depressive state of 40 - 50 points 50 - 60 points have high depression status

REFERENCES:

1. Ilin E.P. Psixologiya emotsiy i chuvstv. - M.: 2008.
2. Izard K. Emotsii cheloveka. – M.: 2008.
3. Psixologiya motivatsii i emotsiy. Pod red.YU.B.Gippenreyter,
4. Falikman M.V.- M.: 2009
- 5.Тойчиева, С. (2023). ПСИХОДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИГРОВОЙ ТЕРАПИИ У ДЕТЕЙ МАЛОГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. Международный бюллетень прикладной науки и технологий , 3 (9), 366–369.
6. Туйчиева, Ш. Ж. (2020). Узбекская семья как главный очаг воспитания. Ученый XXI века, (1 (60)), 53-55.
7. Туйчиева, Ш. Ж. (2016). О ПРОБЛЕМЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОГО САМОРАЗВИТИЯ ПЕДАГОГА. NovalInfo. Ru, 2(42), 212-215.
8. Туйчиева, Ш. Ж. (2012). РАЗВИТИЕ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО МЫШЛЕНИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОЛЛЕЖЕЙ. Педагогические науки, (1), 103-106.
9. Kizi, B. Z. M. (2023). THE DEVELOPMENT OF LOGICAL THINKING OF YOUNGER SCHOOLCHILDREN IN THE LESSONS OF THE SURROUNDING WORLD. European

International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 3(06), 186-189.

10. Bobayeva, Z. M. Q. (2023). Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining intellektual qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish. Science and Education, 4(2), 973-977